

Fundamental Concepts of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a breeding ground of abounds such things such as subfields and ideas. In this article we go a bit further with the core areas of AI, a bit further in the weak vs. the strong AI debate, and some basic philosophical stuff.

1. Artificial Intelligence Core Areas

Machine Learning (ML)

Arthur Samuel coined the term machine learning in 1959 as the subfield of AI concerned with assigning programs to function in situations where they have not been explicitly instructed to take place. Tom Mitchell, a pioneer in the field, provided a formal definition: Based on Mitchell, we define learning as follows: "A computer program is said to learn from experience E with respect to some class of tasks T if its performance at tasks in T , as measured by a performance measure P , improves with experience E " (Mitchell, 1997).

ML is typically categorized into three types:

- Supervised Learning: The algorithm learns from labeled data.
- Unsupervised Learning: The algorithm finds patterns in unlabeled data.
- Reinforcement Learning: The algorithm learns through interaction with an environment.

Example: One of Netflix's recommendation systems — it learns from user behavior to suggest movies and TV shows.

Deep Learning (DL)

DL is an ML's subset inspired by the structure and function of the human brain. Artificial neural networks (ANN) with multiple layers are used to analyze various factors of data. Admittedly, deep learning techniques are often attributed to the 'godfathers' of AI: Yoshua Bengio, Geoffrey Hinton, and Yann LeCun (Goodfellow et al., 2016).

Example: The world champion in the game of Go, defeated by AlphaGo, DeepMind's innovation.

Natural Language Processing (NLP)

A branch of AI where computers interact with human language is NLP. It lets machines 'talk' to humans and speak like humans. This field has been pioneered by Christopher Manning and Jurafsky (Manning & Schütze, 1999; Jurafsky & Martin, 2000).

Example: Real time translation between many languages using Google Translate.

Computer Vision (CV)

CV is the subset of AI focused on making computers see the world around them. Specifically, it concerns how computers learn high level understanding from digital images and videos. Szeliski (2022) are researchers who have made substantial contributions to this field.

Example: Security applications of facial recognition systems.

Robotics

The field of robotics uses AI with engineering to create machines which can work with the physical world. Usually there are other AI fields, such as CV and NLP, that it usually integrates. In this field has been important person Rodney Brooks, former director of the Computer Science and AI Laboratory at MIT (Brooks, 1990).

Example: Boston Dynamics' lovable robots that navigate their way around complex terrain like Star Wars stormtroopers.

Expert Systems

AI programs that mimic human expert's decision making skills are known as Expert Systems. And they were some of the first – actually, the first – truly successful forms of AI software. Edward Feigenbaum, often called the "father of expert systems," was a pioneer in this field (Feigenbaum, 1992).

Example: Systems for medical diagnosis which can suggest a potential diagnosis given certain symptoms.

2. Weak AI vs. Strong AI Debate

The terms "Weak AI" and "Strong AI" were introduced by philosopher John Searle in his 1980 paper "Minds, Brains, and Programs" (Searle, 1980).

Weak AI (Narrow AI)

Weak AI is the build of AI that is meant to accomplish specific tasks. Those we encounter daily are the AI applications. Stuart Russell describes weak AI as "the study of specific problem-solving or reasoning tasks" (Russell & Norvig, 2021).

AI systems that are weak are excellent at doing their specific thing but lack general intelligence. They don't have consciousness or genuine understanding; they simulate cognitive function.

Example: IBM's Watson, which excels at question answering but doesn't understand the meaning of its responses.

Strong AI (Artificial General Intelligence - AGI)

Strong AI is a hypothetical AI which matches or exceeds human intelligence across a range of cognitive tasks. It would be aware, sentient and have mind, able to think and reason as a human.

The notion of Strong AI is also a component of Vernor Vinge, who is a mathematician and science fiction writer, and it is popularized by Ray Kurzweil, a futurist (Kurzweil, 2005).

Strong AI is still the subject of intense debate and research. Some (e.g., Kurzweil), for example, predict it will arrive within decades, while others (e.g., philosopher Hubert Dreyfus, 1992) claim it might be fundamentally impossible.

3. Turing Test and Artificial Consciousness

Turing Test

Proposed by Alan Turing in his seminal 1950 paper "Computing Machinery and Intelligence," the Turing Test was designed to provide an operational definition of intelligence. Turing posed the question, "Can machines think?" It then reformulated it as an imitation game. In this game, an interrogator communicates via text with two participants: a human and a machine. We say that the machine has passed the test (Turing, 1950) if the interrogator cannot reliably distinguish the machine from the human.

The Turing Test has been both influential and controversial:

It advocates a practical, behavior based way of evaluating machine intelligence. Philosopher Daniel Dennett has defended the test, saying that passing it would be a big mile marker in AI development (Dennett, 1998).

Critics, however, point out several limitations:

1. **The Chinese Room Argument:** Giving this thought experiment by philosopher John Searle, he used it to argue that passing the Turing Test does not mean understanding or consciousness. According to Searle (1980), in his scenario, a non-Chinese speaker gets instructions to reply to Chinese messages; they seem to understand Chinese when actually it is not the case.
2. **Superficial Imitation:** To questioners who claim the test rewards shallow language tricks rather than true genius, some argue. Joseph Weizenbaum showed this with ELIZA, a simple program that could seem (and sometimes actually be) enmeshed in meaningful dialogue by means of pattern matching and substitution (Weizenbaum, 1966).
3. **Anthropocentric Bias:** So the test might be biased towards human like intelligence, misusing or undervaluing other kinds.

Even though they were criticized, variations of the Turing test have been used. Keeping the Turing idea relevant in modern AI discourse, the Loebner Prize has been awarded for most human like chatbots.

Artificial Consciousness

Artificial consciousness, or machine consciousness, or synthetic consciousness is the hypothetical property of non biological systems of having a consciousness. With philosophy of mind, cognitive science, neuroscience, and artificial intelligence, this concept intersects.

Key aspects of the artificial consciousness debate include:

1. **The Hard Problem of Consciousness:** It was coined by Philosopher David Chalmers, to describe the challenge of explaining how or why we had qualia or phenomenal experiences. According to Chalmers, no matter how able we are to describe the functional and behavioral aspects of consciousness, we won't be able to elucidate what it really is to be conscious, the "subjective experience," to put it bluntly: the self as it feels itself, the first person experience (Chalmers, 2010).
2. **Global Workspace Theory:** Proposed by Bernard Baars, this theory suggests that consciousness arises from a "global workspace" in which multiple cognitive processes compete for attention. Based on this theory, some AI researchers such as Stan Franklin use this theory as a foundation for cognitive architectures trying to model consciousness (Baars, 1997; Franklin et al, 2002).
3. **Integrated Information Theory (IIT):** IIT's theory, developed by neuroscientist Giulio Tononi, is that consciousness is like a specific kind of information integration within a system. Related to machine consciousness is that any system capable of the right kind of information integration would be conscious (Tononi, 2004).
4. **Higher-Order Thought (HOT) Theories:** Philosophers like David Rosenthal argue that consciousness arises from higher order thoughts about mental states. This perspective has influenced some approaches to machine consciousness (Rosenthal, 1986).

The debate on artificial consciousness is far from settled:

- Some researchers, like Antonio Damasio, argue that consciousness is crucial for higher-level reasoning and decision-making, suggesting that true AGI might require artificial consciousness (Damasio, 1999).
- Others, like Daniel Dennett, argue that consciousness is more of an illusion or "user interface" and that replicating its functional aspects might be sufficient for AGI (Dennett, 1991).
- Skeptics like John Searle maintain that digital computers, operating on syntax alone, could never produce genuine understanding or consciousness (Searle, 1980).

Practical Implications:

The question of machine consciousness has significant ethical and practical implications:

1. Rights and Moral Status: If machines were conscious, should they be given rights or have a moral standing?
2. AI Safety: Understanding consciousness could be crucial for ensuring advanced AI systems behave ethically and align with human values.
3. Uploading and Digital Immortality: Futurists try to dream about the possibility of transferring the human consciousness into machines, and it depends much, good or bad, that we understand the consciousness and it's possible to replicate it in an artificial way.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence is a wide field and expanding fast with its own sub fields and philosophical debates. From practical applications in machine learning and computer vision to profound questions about the intelligence nature and consciousness, AI continues to push the boundaries of technology and human understanding.

However, with the advancement of AI technology, it is important to know these basic concepts. While they also help us understand current AI capabilities, they help us understand the capabilities and, more importantly, critique claims of AI and participate in informed discussions about its future.

The road to AI is still a long one. But if each breakthrough is, it also means new questions and new challenges. As we stand on the brink of potentially revolutionary advancements, one thing is certain: AI's future looks to be as exciting as it is uncertain.

Boldly go where no human or AI has gone before!
Ferhat Sarikaya

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